

INVESTIGATION OF THE FATIGUE FAILURE MECHANISMS FOR STITCHED AND UNSTITCHED UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

C.Zhang¹, M.Jamshidi¹, S.Barnes¹, S.Cauchy-Savona², J. Rouse¹, R.Bradley¹, P.Withers¹, P.Hogg*¹,

¹Northwest Composites Centre, School of Materials, University of Manchester, UK

²School of Engineering and Materials Science, Queen Mary, University of London, UK

* Corresponding author (paul.hogg@manchester.ac.uk)

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1 Introduction

The traditional glass fabrics used in composite structures are usually in the form of two dimensional (2D) fibre architectures. They are relatively inexpensive and usually provide good in-plane mechanical properties. However, most of them have relatively poor through-thickness mechanical properties because the load applied the translaminar direction is predominately carried by the resin matrix. During last two decades, a considerable amount of research has been devoted to improving the through-thickness mechanical properties of composite laminate by developing the 3-D fibre architecture that includes braiding, knitting, weaving and stitching. The purpose of this study is to apply the stitching technologies into the composite materials in wind turbine blades that are designed to have fatigue life of 20 years and more.

A main problem with stitching is that localised damage occurs where the sewing needle and yarn penetrate the materials. Unlike homogeneous metals, the fatigue damage which occurs in the anisotropic composite materials is more complicated. The micro-structural mechanisms of damage accumulation which include fibre breakage, matrix cracking, debonding and delamination occur sometimes independently and sometimes interactively [1]. By using conventional approaches, it is almost impossible to observe the fatigue damage propagation inside a sane sample, as it requires the researcher to destruct the integrality of the fatigue testing sample. By using the non-destructive technique (NDT), it could significantly change the way by which we used to explore fatigue damages in composites materials. In this study, three different NDTs were carried out to detect the cracks and delaminations, which are i) digital image correlation (DIC), ii) thermography, and iii) x-ray tomography.

2 Experimental details

In this study, stitched and unstitched coupon samples made of uniweave glass fabrics were compared. These uniweave fabrics, which are supplied by Carr Reinforcements Ltd, are a type of construction where the unidirectional (UD) fibres are bonded together by a very light polyester thread in the weft direction with negligible crimp. Each composite laminate consist of 8 layers of uniweave fabric. The modified lock stitches were applied into fabrics by using an industrial sewing machine. The 120tex Kevlar-29 thread with tenacity of 185~200cN/Tex from Atlantic Thread and Supply was chosen for the stitching. In total there were five stitching lines applied, for the stitched sample. The vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM), was used to manufacture the composite laminates. Once the laminate was manufactured, it was weighed and cut into smaller coupon samples to the required dimensions by using a water-cooled diamond saw. A typical stitched coupon sample is shown in Fig.1. The dimensions and volume fraction of fibres for both stitched and unstitched samples are listed in Table.1.

ASTM standards D3039-08 and D3479-96 were adopted in this study for measuring the quasi-static tensile properties and tension-tension fatigue properties, respectively. A constant stress ratio ($R = 0.1$) and frequency (5Hz) were applied to all fatigue testing samples.

3 Results

3.1 Fatigue testing results

It was found during the fatigue test, cracks and damages were initiated around stitched in the stitched sample. Unlikely in unstitched samples, the cracks and damages were initiated randomly throughout the sample. This difference is confirmed

by the DIC and thermography results which are presented in the latter sections. Although their fatigue damages were initiated at different locations after a certain number of fatigue cycles, both unstitched and stitched samples failed same way by splitting and fracturing of fibre tows (see Fig.2).

It was also surprisingly found that there was no discernable difference between the stitched and unstitched laminates in the results of their fatigue tests (see Fig.3). It seems those inherent defects around the stitched areas seem not to decrease the fatigue resistance of the uniweave composite material. On the other hand, the polyester threads stitched in the weft direction also seem to introduce cracks and influence the fatigue performance of the uniweave laminates. Thus x-ray thermography was used to inspect the influence of different stitches.

3.2 DIC results

A DIC system Q-400 developed by Dantec Dynamics was also used to track the strains on sample surface. DIC technique can be used for measuring the surface contour, three-dimensional (3D) displacement and strains. In this study, the DIC system Q-400 developed by Dantec Dynamics was used. In order to obtain images of surface strain, the fatigue load was paused at the minimum tensile stress (38.3MPa) after a certain number of cycles, and then quasi-statically moved the maximum tensile stress.

The strains of sample surface between the minimum displacement and the maximum displacement thus were recorded. Before the sample reached 1000 cycles, one measurement was recorded in every 200 cycles; while after the sample reached 1000 cycles one measurement in every 1000 cycles was recorded. In Fig.4, it compares the strains of unstitched sample with stitched sample after 400 cycles and 17,000 cycles, respectively.

In Fig.4 (c and d), it also shows that stitching generates high strain concentration areas along the sample. Within stitched sample, in order to evaluate the difference strains between stitched area and unstitched area, two straight lines were drawn. The history of strain variations over stitched (line 1) and unstitched (line 2) areas were recorded and plotted in Fig.5, respectively. Apart from these two areas, the average strains of unstitched and stitched samples at different fatigue cycles are also plotted in Fig.5. It clearly indicates that the strains on stitching

line are much higher than unstitched area. The strains on stitching line are increasing gradually while the fatigue test is ongoing. However, the average strains of the stitched sample exhibit almost same values as that of the unstitched sample during the fatigue test.

3.2 Thermography results

It is well known that when a material is subjected to mechanical loading, its temperature will change. If the material is loaded above its fatigue limit, then the temperature change can be significant enough to be detected by infra-red thermography. It has been shown [2] that the rise in temperature depends upon the level of applied alternating stress. Passive infra-red thermography has been used previously [3] to examine damage, fatigue and failure mechanisms in a range of different materials including polymer matrix composites. In a non-homogeneous material, a localization of plastic strain can occur around the discontinuities. This strain localization results in a heat dissipation which can be readily detected in real time during fatigue cycling by infra-red thermography.

In this study, a Thermosensorik infra-red camera operating in the 3-5 μ m wavelength band was used to track temperature changes. In the first tests, the temperature variation across the test sample was measured during the application of a static tensile stress after approximately 90% of the cycles to test failure (Fig.6) for both stitched and unstitched samples. The variability in sample temperature was then measured during fatigue cycling for the stitched sample at approximately 90% of its fatigue life (Fig.7). The infra red image collection frequency allowed 7.75 images per fatigue cycle for the loading frequency of 5 Hz.

In Fig.6, it can be seen that the highest sample temperature (white areas) is at the ends of the test piece for both stitched and unstitched samples. The temperature is highest in this area due to frictional heating between the sample and the grips. The temperature distribution in the centre of the sample is similar for both materials, but it is clear that the temperature distribution is not symmetrical across the width of the test piece. This could indicate some variability in sample thickness and/or fibre alignment across the sample width. The stitching is just visible in the infra-red image (Fig.6(b), arrowed) during the application of the static tensile stress, but

can be seen clearly during the application of fatigue loading. Fig.7 shows that there is clearly a greater heat release around the stitching (arrowed) at the highest tensile stress, whilst there is a lower temperature in the stitched area as the load is reduced to the minimum level. The increased heat release around the stitched areas at the highest tensile stress, during the latter stages of the fatigue life of the sample, could be the result of strain localization around the areas of stitching leading to damage evolution in these areas.

3.3 X-ray tomography results

Thanks to the art of reconstructing a sliceable virtual 3D copy of the object from two-dimensional (2D) images, x-ray tomography is becoming increasingly popular [4]. Superior to former two technologies, detailed characterization of fatigue cracking mechanisms inside the materials can thus be evaluated by using x-ray tomography. Up to now, no such study has been published yet for composite materials.

X-ray tomography is a non destructive technique based on absorption of x-rays as they pass through an object. Laboratory x-ray tomography systems typically utilise cone-beam geometry, in which x-rays are produced from a small spot in the source [5]. The sample is mounted on a rotation stage, and the transmitted x-rays are recorded on a pixellated detector. The point-projection geometry typically used in a laboratory set-up is shown in Fig.8 [6].

Geometrical magnification is used to achieve high resolution, which is ultimately limited by the spot-size of the source. During a scan, a series of radiographs are taken as the object rotates over 360 degrees. A 3-D reconstruction of the object is then obtained by using the Feldkamp-Davis-Kress algorithm. In current study, scans were performed using a Nikon Metrology XTH 225 system, which is based on a 225 kV source, having a ~5 micron spot size and a choice of target material, including W, Cu, Mo and Ag. The system has a 14-bit flat panel detector with a 130 micron pixel pitch.

According to the observations of both DIC and thermography, it seems that the stitches are the principal areas initiating failure. But further analysis carried out by x-ray tomography reveals the interlaminar cracks and delaminations also were generated and appeared at other places, not only around stitches.

In Fig.9, it reveals that the interlaminar delaminations dominate the damage propagating process. It is interesting to note that, few delamination or crack occurs at the Kevlar-stitched area. Instead, the delaminations and cracks are more often found along the polyester threads. This phenomenon also can be seen in Fig.10 and Fig.11. Fig.11 compares the propagation of delaminations in a stitched sample at the fatigue cycles of 6,000 and 15,000, respectively. It can be found that the sample generated more delaminations (arrowed, Fig.11(b)) after 15,000 cycles. The resin rich pocket is the vulnerable area where the resin would be stretched under the fatigue load, but the fibre bundles underneath the resin pocket are constrained tightly by Kevlar threads so that delamination is hard to propagate.

4 Conclusions

It was found that the failure mechanisms of stitched and unstitched are mainly control by interlaminar delaminations and fibre splitting. According to the observations of DIC and thermography, stitching area looks more likely to fail under fatigue load, but the results of x-ray tomography indicate Kevlar stitches do not generate main damages during fatigue life. Fibre bundles are considerably constrained by Kevlar threads and behave like a solid and tough unit. As a result, the delaminations and cracks trend to appear at relatively weaker areas where the polyester threads were stitched during the manufacturing process. Possibly, this is the reason that the stitched sample presented similar fatigue properties as unstitched sample.

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Fig.1. Schematic sketch of a typical stitched sample

Fig.2. Typical failure mechanisms of: a) unstitched sample - failed at 48,554 cycles, under 342.5MPa (or 44.2% strength level); b) stitched sample - failed at 87,666 cycles, under 315.1MPa (or 49.2% strength).

Table. 1.

Sample	Width /mm	Thickness /mm	VF%
Unstitched	15.42±0.49	4.98±0.13	55.8
Stitched	20.07±0.11	5.22±0.12	55.9

values behind the ± are standard deviations;
VF%: volume fraction of fibres

(a) (b) (c) (d)

Fig.4. Principal strain for samples: (a) unstitched after 400 cycles; (b) unstitched after 17,000cycles; (c) stitched after 400 cycles; and (d) stitched after 17,000 cycles. Arrows indicate the stitching lines.

Fig. 3. Maximum tensile stress level to cycles-to-failure curves of stitched and unstitched under tension-tension fatigue load

Fig.5. Variations of the average strain in fatigue tests.

Fig.6. Infra-red thermography images showing temperature variation across (a) non-stitched and (b) stitched test samples at approximately 90% of their respective fatigue lives. Areas of stitching are arrowed. White colour represents the highest temperature and blue the lowest temperature.

Fig.7. Infra-red images taken through through 17,000 fatigue cycles for the stitched sample (1 and 5 are minimum tensile stress, 3 is maximum tensile stress)

Fig.8. Point-projection geometry of laboratory based x-ray micro-tomography.

Fig.9. Tomography images of unstitched (top) and stitched (bottom) samples tested after 15,000 fatigue cycles (just before the sample failed) under the maximum fatigue stress of 382.9MPa.

Fig.10. The distribution of delaminations and cracks in the Kevlar-stitched sample at different positions

Fig.11. Crack propagations in stitched sample under the maximum fatigue stress of 382.9MPa: a) after 6,000 cycles; b) after 15,000 cycles